

THE ACTIVITIES OF THE SAMARKAND BRANCH OF THE JOINT-STOCK LEASING COMPANY "UZSELKHOZMASHLIZING" TO MEET THE DEMAND FOR LEASING SERVICES

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Abstract. The article discusses leasing operations, the use of leasing in a short time, to form fixed assets, to actively pursue an investment policy, stimulating the development of private, small and medium-sized businesses without creating additional administrative bodies, exclusively by economic methods.

Keywords: Leasing, operation, business, enterprises, banking institutions, production.

ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ САМАРКАНДСКОГО ФИЛИАЛА АКЦИОНЕРНОГО ЛИЗИНГОВОГО ОБЩЕСТВА «УЗСЕЛЬХОЗМАШЛИЗИНГ» ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ СПРОСА НА ЛИЗИНГОВЫЕ УСЛУГИ

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются лизинговые операции, использование лизинга в сжатые сроки, для формирования основных фондов, для активного проведения инвестиционной политики, стимулирования развития частного, малого и среднего бизнеса без создания дополнительных органов управления, исключительно экономическими методами.

Ключевые слова: Лизинг, операция, бизнес, предприятия, банковские учреждения, производство.

INTRODUCTION

Leasing is one of the main financial instruments that allow large-scale capital investments in the development of the material and technical base of any production. Banking institutions and large industrial enterprises are showing great interest in investing in the means of production of the domestic industry. Given the current economic situation and the urgent need to revive investment activity, the problem of leasing development is of particular relevance for the state.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Joint Stock Leasing Company "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" was established on October 30, 1999. The founders of the company are legal entities and individuals. Joint Stock Leasing Company "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" is focused on leasing agricultural machinery to agricultural producers (sherkats and farmers, MTP and AMTP) with stable production and financial activities. The company is open to cooperation and problem solving in search of optimal ways to finance the material and technical needs of its customers.

The main activity of the company is the delivery on leasing terms of a wide range of agricultural machinery, domestic and foreign production.

Also, in the conditions of a transitional economy, one of the most important activities of the ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" is participation in the program of technical re-equipment of domestic agricultural producers (shirkats and farms of MTP and AMTP), the scale of activity

and national economic significance of which allows minimizing financial risks in the implementation of leasing projects.

The Uzelkhoz mashleasing company has established business relations with leading foreign and domestic manufacturers and suppliers of agricultural equipment, which gives a wide range of choices for the most attractive leasing object for the company's customers. Today, our company is ready to implement specific schemes and mutually beneficial projects, we are sure that cooperation with us will open new opportunities for your business in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Information on the structure of the Authorized Fund and shareholders of Uzelkhoz mashlizing1. Authorized Fund - 9350 million soums.

2. Nominal value of 1 share - 2200.0 sum.

3. Total shares: 4,250,000 pieces. of them:

a) simple nominal - 4,230,000 pieces.

b) privileged nominal - 20,000 pieces.

4. Total shareholders 659. of which:

a) legal entities and individuals, residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan - 649. b) legal entities and individuals, non-residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan - 10.

One of the leading divisions The Uzelkhoz mashlizing company is its Samarkand branch, which carries out leasing operations not only in the Samarkand region, but also in the southern regions of the country.

Experience shows that the use of leasing allows no update in a short time and form fixed assets, actively pursue an investment policy, stimulating the development of private, small and medium-sized businesses carried out without creating additional administrative bodies, exclusively by economic methods.

RESULTS

As you know, the leasing of agricultural machinery is one of the most important tools for reforming economic relations in the agricultural sector and is under the close attention of the government. Therefore, the main activity of the Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzelkhoz mashlizing" is the implementation of the Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (Table 1)

Table 1

Information on the activities of the Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzelkhoz mashlizing" as of 1.01.2022

No.	Agricultural brand technology	plan for 2021(PCS.)	Issued equipment as of 01/01/2022(PCS)	Difference -, + (PCS)	Number of concluded contracts as of 01.01.2022 (PCS)	Number of advance payments issued as of 01.02.2022 none(PCS)
According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 424						
one	TTZ-80.10	22	17	-5	22	2
2	TTZ-80.11	128	75	-53	112	fifteen
3	TL-100 A. TL-5060	ten	13	3	21	2
	Total:	160	105	-55	155	19
According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 486						

one	KU-4 VM	35	24	-eleven	29	one
2	Tirkama	35	fifteen	-twenty	eighteen	-
3	KIR-1.5	36	22	-fourteen	25	-
four	KOS-2.1	four	-	-four	one	-
5	RMU-0.5	-	ten	ten	eighteen	-
6	OVH-600	four	fourteen	ten	16	one
7	ORPD-12 M	twenty	49	29	thirty	-
eight	KChU-3.6	-	ten	ten	17	-
9	OG-101 AIDA	-	35	35	35	-
ten	Plow	-	6	6	eleven	one
eleven	OShN-1-300	-	eleven	eleven	13	-
	Total:	134	196	62	213	3
	Total:	294	301	7	368	22

As can be seen from the table below The Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" is carrying out certain work to implement the decisions of the government. At the same time, it should be noted that certain positions of the resolutions have not been implemented. This indicates the presence of problems in the development of leasing services and the improvement of the marketing strategy. In addition to the issuance of equipment for leasing, the Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" carries out such a type of leasing as the acceptance of equipment for special storage (Table 2).

Table 2.

Equipment accepted for special storage

No№	Technique for special storage in 2010	Qty	Received January 2010	Balance as of February 1, 2010
one	Cultivator	19	one	eighteen
2	KChU-3.6	one	0	one
3	KIR-1.5	17	one	16
four	KOS	2	one	one
5	OShN-1-300	2	0	2
6	Plow	2	one	one
7	Plow	2	0	2
eight	Trailer	13	four	9
9	RMU-0.5	5	one	four
ten	OVH-600	ten	0	ten
eleven	OG AIDA 101	0	0	0
12	ORPD-12 M	0	0	0
	Total	73	9	64

To measure customer satisfaction The Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" has introduced a system for accounting claims for agricultural machines issued on credit. (Table 3).

Table 3

Information about complaints Samarkand branch of ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" for 2022

No№	Number of complaints (pcs.)	Liquidated (pcs.)	Not liquidated (pcs.)

one.	16	16	0
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As the table data shows, 16 claims were registered in 2022, and all claims were promptly liquidated. At the same time, the presence of complaints requires a careful selection of leasing objects to prevent such cases. In our opinion, leasing companies need to have specialists in the technical condition of equipment on their staff.

DISCUSSION

To increase customer confidenceThe Samarkand branch of the ALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" is actively working to monitor the provided leasing services. The bodies of the State Technical Control are also involved in this event. (Table 4)

Table 4

Information about the ongoing monitoring of leasing services

№	Total issued equipment according to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 424 (pcs.)	This included monitoring	
		From the side of the branch (pcs.)	From the side of Gostekhkontrolya (pcs.)
one	1356	1239	916

The development of leasing is aimed at the development of all forms of ownership in agriculture, in connection with which it is advisable to analyze the impact of leasing on the formation of private property. According to the Samarkand branchALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" in recent years has been transferred to private ownership of 1475 pieces of equipment. (table 5)

Table 5

Information on the transfer of agricultural machinery to private ownership

Total	According to the Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers			
	No. 345	No. 424	No. 389	No. 486
1475	fourteen	410	7	1044

CONCLUSION

Satisfying the demand for leasing services is directly related to the assortment policy of the Samarkand branch of Uzselkhoz mashlizing. Table 2.6 provides data on the range and structure of leased equipment. As the data show, TTZ tractors occupy the main place in the range of leasing services.

A significant place in the marketing activities of the Samarkand branchALC "Uzselkhoz mashlizing" is occupied by the pricing policy. As you know, the prices of leasing services depend on the price characteristics of agricultural machinery manufacturers and leasing conditions.

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